

D5.3 OS and RDM learning paths for Solid Earth sciences communities

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents the learning path on “Open Science and Research Data Management in Solid Earth Sciences” elaborated by EPOS, the European Plate Observing System. The training targets researchers, students, and RI managers, as well as prospective trainers in this field, emphasizing continuous improvement and feedback.

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<i>Reviewed by:</i>	Stefano Cacciaguerra	INGV	25/07/2024
	Daniele Bailo	INGV/EPOS	02/08/2024
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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

<i>Terminology/Acronym</i>	<i>Definition</i>
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
OS	Open Science
RDM	Research Data Management
RI	Research Infrastructure
SES	Solid Earth Science
TCS	Thematic Core Service
ToT	Train-of-Trainers

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable presents the learning path on “Open Science and Research Data Management in Solid Earth Sciences” and the relevant training resources elaborated by EPOS, the European Plate Observing System.

The learning path focuses on providing basic knowledge of Open Science, FAIR and Research Data Management (RDM) principles in the context of solid Earth sciences and leveraging EPOS to implement them in practice. The training plan is intended to foster skills in accessing and using EPOS data, with specific modules dedicated to interoperability, data management basics, and hands-on sessions using EPOS's data portal.

The training targets researchers, students, and RI managers, as well as prospective trainers in this field, emphasizing continuous improvement and feedback.

2 Introduction – Context

2.1 Current practices and challenges in the disciplinary field

In the last decade, integrating distributed resources across regional, national, and international data centres and Research Infrastructures (RIs) has become essential for multidisciplinary research and innovation. This is particularly true for Earth Science, where diverse measurements are needed to understand complex physical phenomena. Combining data such as historical seismic sequences, InSAR imaging, and GPS data can provide detailed insights into fault systems. Different communities co-exist within solid Earth science, each of them providing domain-specific data and services. Each community includes a number of different RIs operating at national level that collect, manage and manipulate data according to their mission and specific policies. This makes the SES data environment very rich but also incredibly complex. Before the advent of large-scale research infrastructures, this resulted in an extremely complex and fragmented landscape encompassing a wide amount of heterogeneous data types and formats, processing levels, community standards and vocabularies.

Accessing these heterogeneous data sources requires both transparent access to knowledge and a robust technical framework to manage data through open systems. Open Science (OS) principles, emphasizing openness and accessibility, align with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, which are increasingly recognized by the European Commission as foundational for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and essential for participating in EU projects involving data management. In this landscape, the European Plate Observing System (EPOS), stands as the only pan-European research infrastructure for solid Earth science. EPOS integrates data, software, and services from various subdomains, facilitating comprehensive and interoperable data access. It supports over 250 research

infrastructures across 26 countries, monitoring the European tectonic plate through extensive sensor networks and remote sensing.

Given EPOS's role as a landmark in Open Science within Europe, this learning path centres on leveraging the EPOS infrastructure to implement and practice Open Science and Research Data Management (RDM) principles. The training covers general RDM practices in solid Earth science but focuses on EPOS's implementation of OS and FAIR principles, demonstrating best practices and practical applications through the EPOS portal.

Training is a continuous action during the lifecycle of a Research Infrastructure (RI), which has to be calibrated to the specific stages of the lifecycle. During implementation and construction, for instance, training is an important element for strengthening the capacity building of the involved community, since it contributes to increasing awareness of the potentiality in using and further developing the RI. It is even more important during the operational phase, which is the current stage of the EPOS RI. Indeed, it is a relevant component of the users' strategy, since it contributes to engaging external users increasing the capacities to access and use the EPOS RI and its data portal. Training is particularly important for the EPOS internal community, including data providers and national research organizations engaged in supporting the RI operation. Our experience in the previous phases of the implementation of the infrastructure shows that training can effectively speed up and strengthen this process. It is also a contribution to the EPOS ERIC human research plan because it contributes to strengthen expertise and/or new skills for the management of the EPOS RI.

The operational phase of the EPOS RI requires a dedicated training plan. The peculiar stage of the EPOS RI, namely the operational phase, affects the priorities and the strategic actions envisaged in the training plan as well as the timeline for undertaking related initiatives. The EPOS training plan has the following key objectives:

- Fostering Open Science and Research Data Management in solid Earth science
- Fostering the access and use of the EPOS data and services

- Strengthening skills for RI managers (also in collaboration with t5.1 and the RItrainPlus project.)

To achieve these objectives through the adopted methodology it is fundamental to identify the target audiences. The EPOS training is designed for the following target audiences:

- Researchers (both part of the EPOS Research Infrastructure and belonging to the long tail of science)
- Students and young researchers
- RI managers (from EPOS Executive Coordination Office, Thematic Communities and other relevant Research Infrastructures)
- General public

Because of the recent launch of the EPOS Operational Phase (April 2023), the priority has been assigned to the first two above-mentioned target audiences. The third one will rely on support from external projects and initiatives (such as RITRAINPlus). The last target audience will be engaged at a later stage.

The design of the learning path relies on identifying a few learning objectives (what learners need to know and to do) structured in online presentations and use cases implemented together with the EPOS Thematic Communities (TCS). In particular, to achieve the goal of fostering OS and RDM in solid Earth science a specific learning path has been dedicated to interoperability (through data, metadata, semantics and webservice), as the cornerstone of a truly open and FAIR approach, as well as to the implementation of the FAIR principles in viable practices. The EPOS RI is used as an example or as a good practice for testing. Materials have been implemented with basic concepts re handling data, datasets and creating and publishing databases, dedicated both to young researchers and PhD students. At the same time, training on fostering the access and use of the EPOS data portal was prioritised and materials were implemented essentially through use cases for researchers within and outside the EPOS community.

Learning Path and Training Materials on OS and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences

The implementation of the EPOS Training requires creating, managing and delivering training materials as well as to define the lesson programs and the logistics. This deliverable describes the work undertaken in the context of T5.3 to design and implement a training path on OS, FAIR and RDM specific to the Solid Earth Science Community and the resulting collection of training material. The evaluation of the training initiatives is periodically carried out using dedicated questionnaires, interviews and surveys as well as impact assessment of Training activities (through KPIs and qualitative indicators).

3 Learning Path

3.1 Methodology

3.1.1 Definition of Learning Path (objectives, practices covered & challenges addressed, targeted communities)

This course is intended as a learning path to engage users (mainly researchers, PhD students, but also teachers) who want to see OS and RDM in practice in the context of solid Earth science (SES). This should ideally be part of a normal practice fostering lifelong learning. It also outlines the agenda and main topics for Train-of-Trainers events and provides supporting materials to all those interested in organising training courses on Open Science, FAIR and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences. All the supplementary materials described below are designed to facilitate this type of activity and provide new trainers with FAIR-by-Design reusable and customisable training materials addressing both prospective trainers and researchers/students.

In Europe, EPOS is the landmark for Open Science in the context of SES, having carried out a decades-long work of harmonisation and integration of data from different subdomains, data sources and data types. For this reason, while in the training we provide some general elements that frame the broader concepts of data and RDM practices in SES, the core part of the training is designed to show how OS and FAIR principles are implemented in the EPOS portal, and how researchers can reuse them according to the best practices.

We build on EPOS' experience of engaging researchers in various solid Earth science subdomains and the format is being progressively modified to reflect the user feedback.

Competences targeted:

- Understanding of basic OS/FAIR/RDM concepts

- Recognising OS/FAIR principles and practices in the SES context and in the EPOS infrastructure in particular
- Using the EPOS Data Portal to discover and reuse FAIR data, services, and scientific products.

3.1.2 Modules

The structure envisaged for this learning path is quite simple and lightweight, with two mandatory modules:

- **Module 1** - Basic OS and FAIR concepts in the SES domain and an introduction of the approach adopted by the EPOS Research Infrastructure to implement key OS and FAIR;
- **Module 2** - Introduction of the EPOS infrastructure, a walkthrough of the EPOS data portal and its main features, introducing the different thematic services and basic functionalities, and a hands-on session based on different scientific use cases.

Along to these two main modules, we provide 2 optional modules:

- **Module 0** - Basic introduction to data and RDM for beginners
- **Module 3** - Focus on Interoperability, metadata and integration.

Although our experience is that many of the attendees of module 1 and 2 are already familiar with the topics mentioned in module 0, while not all training participants are interested in learning the technical details of interoperability, the modules are made available so that Training organizers and facilitators can adapt the content to the prevalent audience.

3.2 Design of Training Materials

The proposed training materials are largely based on existing materials by experts from the EPOS community, repurposed to adhere to the scope of this particular learning path.

Figure.1 Representation of the training materials and path

They are composed by:

- A learning plan and a syllabus (described in this document)
- Slides with speaker’s notes
- A facilitator guide, addressing different aspects of the organisation and delivery of the training (format, layout, description of the activities, etc)
- A collection of use cases to be used in the walkthrough and hands-on sessions, and of the related forms for assessment and feedback.
- A file with additional resources that training facilitators can use for providing additional materials, or students can use to deepen some of the topics covered during the training.

3.2.1 Compliance To The FAIR-By-Design Methodology:

All materials are provided on editable supports (e.g. PPT slides) and complete with licensing information, as well as with a plan of the learning path and notes and indications for Training facilitators.

4 Description: Modules And Activities

4.1 Module 1 - An Introduction to Open Science, FAIR Principles and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences - Open Science, FAIR and EPOS

An overview of basic Open Science and FAIR RDM concepts with examples from the field of SES, and an introduction to how Open and FAIR principles are implemented in practice within the EPOS RI, with some references to its global counterparts.

Main Content: PPTx Slideset with presenter’s notes.

Supporting material: OS and RDM in SES- Additional resources

Title	An Introduction to Open Science, FAIR Principles and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences - Open Science, FAIR and EPOS
Abstract / Description	This is the first of two mandatory modules in the Skills4EOSC Open Science and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences Learning path. It offers an overview of basic Open Science and FAIR RDM concepts with examples from the field of SES, and an introduction to how Open and FAIR principles are implemented in practice within the EPOS RI, with some references to its global counterparts. There are no prerequisites to attend the module but a basic knowledge of the domain of Solid Earth Science will make the learner's experience more fulfilling.
Author(s)	EPOS
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Solid Earth Science, FAIR, EPOS, interoperability, RDM
*Version Date	v1.0 09/2024
URL to Resource	https://zenodo.org/records/13682347
Resource URL Type	DOI

License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	Researchers, PHD students in Solid Earth Science, Data Stewards
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (MS PPTX)
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of basic OS/FAIR/RDM concepts • Recognising of OS/FAIR principles and practices in the SES context and in the EPOS infrastructure in particular
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginners, Intermediate

4.2 Module 2 - EPOS Data Portal Training: Introduction To The EPOS Infrastructure And EPOS Data Portal Walkthrough (Including Hands-On Session)

Brief presentation of the EPOS infrastructure and demonstration of how the EPOS data portal can be used to discover, visualise, and reuse SES data and scientific products. This module introduces the hands-on session.

Main Content: PPTx Slideset with presenter’s notes.

Supporting material: recorded video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-dD2sMn-X5M>

4.2.1 Hands-On Session

In this session, participants are invited to access the EPOS Data portal, presented with one or more scientific use cases and asked to use the portal to complete some tasks related to the use case. They can self-assess their performance through a form, and provide feedback on the difficulties they find. A facilitator is available the whole time to answer questions and provide tips, and they provide a walkthrough the exercises at the end of the session.

Main Content: Document with EPOS Data Portal Scientific use cases

Supporting material: recorded video of hands-on exercise

<https://youtu.be/YeqW1Qp1L6g?feature=shared> (walkthrough starts at min 42)

Assess & feedback form material

Title	EPOS Data Portal Training: Introduction to the EPOS Infrastructure and EPOS Data Portal Walkthrough (Including Hands-On Session)
Abstract / Description	This is the second of two mandatory modules in the Skills4EOSC Open Science and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences Learning path. It offers an introduction of the EPOS infrastructure and a demonstration of how the EPOS data portal can be used to discover, visualise, and reuse SES data and scientific products. This module introduces a hands-on session where trainees can experiment with the portal.
Author(s)	EPOS
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Solid Earth Science, FAIR, EPOS, interoperability, RDM
*Version Date	v1.0 09/2024
URL to Resource	https://zenodo.org/records/13682396 https://zenodo.org/records/13683830
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	Researchers, PHD students in Solid Earth Science, Data Stewards
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (MS PPTX) Document With Scientific Use Cases (MS DOCX)
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of basic OS/FAIR/RDM concepts • Recognising of OS/FAIR principles and practices in the SES context and in the EPOS infrastructure in particular
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginners, Intermediate

4.3 Module 0 - Data, Databases and Data Sharing in Solid Earth Sciences: An introduction - From Basic Definitions to the European Regulation (Optional)

A 101 module especially useful for undergraduates, PHD students, secondary school teachers etc providing general definitions of data, datasets, databases as well as basic orientation regarding RDM in the context of solid Earth science

Main Content: PPTx Slideset with presenter’s notes.

Title	Data, Databases and Data Sharing in Solid Earth Sciences: An Introduction - From Basic Definitions to the European Regulation (Optional)
Abstract / Description	This module is propaedeutic to the two mandatory modules in the Skills4EOSC Open Science and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences Learning path. It offers very basic definitions and concepts related to data and data manipulation in the context of SES. It is recommended for beginners in the field of Data Science.
Author(s)	EPOS
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Solid Earth Science, FAIR, EPOS, interoperability, RDM
*Version Date	v1.0 09/2024
URL to Resource	https://zenodo.org/records/13646664
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO
Target Group (Audience)	Undergraduate and PHD students in Solid Earth Science, Secondary school teachers, generic audiences
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (MS PPTX)

Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of basic OS/FAIR/RDM concepts • Recognising of OS/FAIR principles and practices in the SES context and in the EPOS infrastructure in particular
Expertise (Skill) Level	Beginners

4.4 Module 3 - Focus on Interoperability: The EPOS Approach (Optional)

A more technical discussion of interoperability in the context of SES Research Infrastructures and EPOS in particular, suitable for learners who have more time and interest in getting more information about how the RI works, IT people, Data Providers and Research Infrastructure professionals.

Main Content: PPTx Slideset with presenter’s notes.

Supporting video material and additional resources: <https://www.geo-inquire.eu/dissemination/training-activities/epos-metadata-training>

Title	Focus On Interoperability: The EPOS Approach (Optional)
Abstract / Description	This module is offered as an optional addition to the two mandatory modules in the Skills4EOSC Open Science and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences Learning path. It offers more detailed knowledge on the approach to interoperability adopted in EPOS (and followed by other infrastructures in this field) for audiences with an interest in IT and data science.
Author(s)	EPOS
Primary Language	English
Keyword(s)	Solid Earth Science, FAIR, EPOS, interoperability, RDM
*Version Date	v1.0 09/2024
URL to Resource	https://zenodo.org/records/13682759
Resource URL Type	DOI
License	CC by international 4.0
Access Cost	NO

Target Group (Audience)	IT Professionals, Data Stewards and other Data Professionals, RI staff
Learning Resource Type	Presentation (MS PPTX)
Learning Outcome	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of basic OS/FAIR/RDM concepts • Recognising of OS/FAIR principles and practices in the SES context and in the EOSC infrastructure in particular
Expertise (Skill) Level	Intermediate, Advanced

4.4.1 Additional Activities

Depending on the time available for the course, facilitators can decide to add interactive discussions and flipped classroom moments to increase the activities of the learners' group. This could be especially beneficial in case the trainees are prospective trainers themselves (ToT). In the training plan we offer some input for discussion.

Main content: Facilitator guide

5 Pilots

5.1 Pilot Delivery

Pilots are being run to test the learning path and feedback is collected from participants. Additional materials dedicated to trainers are envisaged to facilitate reuse (in particular: collections of scientific use cases). The training is delivered live online, and it is composed by two modules, one introducing OS and FAIR in solid Earth science and the EPOS infrastructure and the other based on a learning-by-doing approach focussing on hands-on activities and Q&A. The first module is also available as a standalone introduction to the portal, although we encourage interested participants in attending the interactive training.

The success rate in performing the tasks that are part of the hands-on session, together with the specific feedback on it and the response to a set of questions to assess the participants' level of satisfaction with the platform and with the training content are collected and analysed to improve the next versions.

Prospective trainers are also supposed to successfully complete this first-level training. Additionally, they are presented with a set of scientific use cases they can use in further training and encouraged to create their own. The latter point is very important because the main target audience of this learning path are researchers and PHDs/YCR, so the ability to propose use cases of interest for the specific domain they come from effectively facilitates learning and can be a factor in engaging them in using the services and data available.

Feedback from trainers who reused the materials will be sought to make sure that the use case collection reflects their needs and is useful to create new ones. Trainers will be encouraged to add the new use cases to the collection.

5.2 Pilot Outcomes

The learning path structure was piloted in an online training event held in January 2024. The target group were SES researchers at different career

stages, who are also the main end-users of the EPOS Data Portal and its data/services. This group has been identified as potential trainers, as the portal provides access to data essential for further research, and is used in teaching at universities. Participation was much higher than anticipated, peaking at 182 attendees, with slightly fewer completing the training. More than one-third of the attendees provided feedback after the training.

Smaller training events were carried out after the pilot, and the key feedback is reported in the graphics below.

5.3 Feedback and Lessons Learned

5.3.1 January Pilot

Among the respondents, 48% identified as scientists, 36% as ECR or students, 6% as IT Experts, 3% as government officials, and another 3% as National EPOS nodes representatives. Around 50% of the users reported being experienced users (implying some experience in programming/handling data), which is important to consider when planning future training sessions. Due to the high participation, the hands-on part presented some difficulties. This limiting factor was reflected in the evaluation. The other modules received almost exclusively positive feedback, with the overall evaluation for the pilot averaging close to 9/10 regarding (i) support for the proposed approach to training; (ii) usefulness of the knowledge gained and (iii) intention to use the EPOS Data Portal again.

Key feedback from Training in January 2024:

How would you evaluate this approach for training?

71 responses

Figure 2. Key feedback from Training in January 2024 (x-axis: a scale from 0 = worthless to 10 = perfect / y-axis: number of responses)

Do you think you will use the EOSC Data Portal again?

71 responses

Figure 3. Key feedback from Training in January 2024 (x-axis a scale of 0 = no to 10 = definitely / y-axis: number of responses)

The issue with the hands-on session was noted as a lesson learned, and the instructional design was updated to split participants into different groups for larger sessions (>50). Suggestions to have smaller training groups to enhance interaction between participants and trainers were also considered. During the period, our team replicated the training structure on other occasions with smaller groups, receiving very positive feedback.

Additionally, discussions with colleagues from other tasks in WP5 resulted in expanding the training's focus to include optional modules on a basic introduction to FAIR data and RDM in the field as well as an introduction to

interoperability in the EPOS/SES framework. These optional models are described above. Additionally, the task expanded and differentiated the use cases based on the EPOS ERIC platform workflow.

5.3.1 Key Feedback From Other Training Events – Hybrid Event @ BGS In May 2024:

How would you evaluate this approach for training?

33 responses

Figure 4. Key feedback from hybrid event @ BGS in May 2024 (x-axis: a scale from 0 = worthless to 10 = perfect | y-axis: number of responses)

Do you think you will use the EPOS Data Portal again?

33 responses

Figure 5. Key feedback from hybrid event @ BGS in May 2024 (x-axis a scale of 0 = no to 10 = definitely | y-axis: number of responses)

6 Discussion – Next Steps

Additional modules on specific services/groups of services are being developed. The idea is that these can be added or not depending on the specific subdomain the trainees belong. Some of the EPOS thematic communities (TCS) also provide materials on the usage of data in their specific subdomain (e.g. Induced Seismicity). In some cases, these materials are also compliant with the FAIR-by-design methodology, while in others (especially in case of pre-existing materials) an ongoing effort to improve their reusability is being carried out. The community can participate in this effort by sharing learning resources and making them FAIR-by-design and by providing feedback on the existing materials, in a perspective of continuous improvement.

This action aims at disseminating a culture of Open Science in the field of Solid Earth Sciences, also in line with EPOS' strategic objective of engaging a much wider pool of potential users for EPOS Data Portal, and supports Skill4EOSC's long-term ambition of developing a network of Competence Centres, currently under development.

A much longer version (30 hours) of the training with more space to OS basics, Research Data Management and to scientific use cases is being developed for specifically addressing PHD students (lessons plans expected for second half of 2024) and will be tested in at least one of the EPOS partner countries. This version of the training is intended to become part of university curricula, so it is very different in scope. It assumes that participants, while possessing specific expertise in the solid Earth science domain, do not necessarily have prior knowledge of open science and research data management concepts, making it necessary to include several modules on this topic.

7 Links to Additional Documentation

- Web page: <https://www.epos-eu.org/communication/news/epos-data-portal-online-training>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/events/eposdataportalonlinetraining7154055256941682688/>
- Intro and demo: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-dD2sMn-X5M>
- Hands-on exercise instructions and feedback <https://forms.gle/1yB2KVz2kNW1mFweA> <https://youtu.be/YeqW1Qp1L6g>
- Recording of the whole webinar (longer version; 1h15min; including the walk-through and exercises), which were made available to registered participants only: <https://youtu.be/YeqW1Qp1L6g>
- Metadata training videos:
 - https://www.geo-inquire.eu/fileadmin/videos/20231019_Training_EPOS_Metadata/20231019_EPOS_Metadata_training_within_Geo-INQUIRE_part1_Daniele_Bailo.mp4
 - https://www.geo-inquire.eu/fileadmin/videos/20231019_Training_EPOS_Metadata/20231019_EPOS_Metadata_training-within_geo-INQUIRE_part2_Rossana_Paciello.mp4

8 Reusing the Learning Path and Training materials

You are welcome to reuse these materials. If you want to start developing your own training material based on this one, simply clone this training material set for your own purposes and start with your customisation.

Please make sure you're using the latest version of the training materials. Each file is provided with information about the version and last update. Resource bundles are also provided with Readme, Licence and Machine-readable citation files to help you providing proper attribution for the source materials.

If you have any questions related to the materials, their version, and/or more generally to the EPOS Research Infrastructure or EPOS Data portal please, as well as any feedback and suggestions to improve the materials contact us at communication@epos-eric.eu.

9 References

To create this training path and the relevant materials, we built upon the following resources.

No	Description/Link
Educational Resources and Presentations	
R1	Basili, R. - Building and using databases in Earth Sciences - Creazione e uso dei database nelle Scienze della Terra - Corso di Dottorato in Scienze Della Terra - Sapienza Università di Roma, 2024
R2	Data Governance and Legislative Strategies for FAIR Research - Brizioli, S., Cacciaguerra, S., Colcelli, V., Locati, M., Schirru L., 2024
R3	Bailo, D, Cocco, M. , Tanlongo, F. - EPOS Data Portal: the practice of FAIR principles in Solid Earth Sciences - 11/01/2024
R4	Michalek, J., Nedrebø, H. Tanlongo, F. – Open Science, FAIR and EPOS – EPOS pilot training 25/01/2024
R5	Geyer Traver, A., Dorado Garcia, O. EPOS-ES Summer School 2024 Geosciencias En Abierto 098/07/2024
R6	Bailo, D., Paciello, R. 19/10/2023, EPOS Metadata Training within Geo-INQUIRE https://www.geo-inquire.eu/dissemination/training-activities/epos-metadata-training
Publications	
R7	Bailo D, Paciello R, Sbarra M, Rabissoni R, Vinciarelli V and Cocco M (2020) Perspectives on the Implementation of FAIR Principles in Solid Earth Research Infrastructures. <i>Front. Earth Sci.</i> 8:3. doi: 10.3389/feart.2020.00003
R8	D. Bailo, K.G. Jeffery, K. Atakan, L. Trani, R. Paciello, V. Vinciarelli, J. Michalek, A. Spinuso, Data integration and FAIR data management in Solid Earth Science, in <i>Annals of Geophysics</i> , vol. 65 No. 2 (2022), Special issue: EPOS a Research Infrastructure in solid Earth: open science and innovation. Doi: https://doi.org/10.4401/ag-8742 .
R9	Bailo, D. et al. (2023). Integrated Access to Multidisciplinary Data Through Semantically Interoperable Services in a Metadata-Driven Platform for Solid Earth Science. In: Garoufallou, E., Vlachidis, A. (eds) <i>Metadata and Semantic Research. MTSR 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science</i> , vol 1789. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-39141-5_20
R10	Paciello, R., Trani, L., Bailo, D., Sbarra, M. (2023). EPOS-DCAT-AP 2.0 – State of Play on the Application Profile for Metadata Exchange in the EPOS RI. In: Garoufallou, E., Vlachidis, A. (eds) <i>Metadata and Semantic Research. MTSR 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science</i> , vol 1789. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-39141-5_21
R11	Paciello, R., Trani, L., Bailo, D., Vinciarelli, V., Sbarra, M. (2023). SHAPEness: A SHACL-Driven Metadata Editor. In: Garoufallou, E., Vlachidis, A. (eds) <i>Metadata and Semantic Research. MTSR 2022. Communications in Computer and Information Science</i> , vol 1789. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-39141-5_23
Other Resources	

R12	Gallagher, R.; Falster, D.; Maitner, B.; Salguero-Gómez, R; Vandvik, V.; Pearse, W.; Schneider, F.; Kattge, J. Alroy, J.; Ankenbrand, M.; Andrew, S.; Balk, M.; Bland, L.; Boyle, B.; Bravo Avila, C.; Brennan, I.; Carthey, A.; Catullo, R.; Cavazos, B.; Enquist, B.. (2019). The Open Traits Network: Using Open Science principles to accelerate trait-based science across the Tree of Life. 10.32942/osf.io/kac45.
R14	Filiposka, S., Mishev, A., & Leister, C. (2024, June 10). FAIR-by-Design Microlearning. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11548062
R15	Filiposka, S. (2023, December 4). FAIR-by-Design Methodology:How to Develop FAIR Materials. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10256852
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Appendix I. Course syllabus

1 Course Details

1.1 Course Title

Open Science and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences: An Introduction Based on the EPOS Research Infrastructure.

1.2 Contact Information

For further information about scheduled courses please refer to <https://www.epos-eu.org/> or communication@epos-eric.eu.

1.3 Location and Formats

Classroom, Online and Blended courses are available.

2 Course Description

This course is intended as a training course engaging users (mainly researchers, PhD students, but also teachers) who want to see OS and RDM in practice in the context of Solid Earth Science (SES). This should ideally be part of a normal practice fostering lifelong learning.

It also outlines the agenda and main topics for Train-of-Trainers events and provides supporting materials to all those interested in organising training courses on Open Science, FAIR and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences. All the supplementary materials described below are designed to facilitate this type of activity and provide new trainers with FAIR-by-Design reusable and customisable training materials addressing both prospective trainers and researchers/students.

In Europe, EPOS is the landmark for Open Science in the context of SES, having carried out a decades-long work of harmonisation and integration of data from different subdomains, data sources and data types. For this reason, while in the training we provide some general elements that frame the broader concepts of data and RDM practices in SES, the core part of the training is designed to show how OS and FAIR principles are implemented in the EPOS portal, and how researchers can reuse them according to the best practices.

We build on EPOS' experience of engaging researchers in various Solid Earth Science subdomains and the format is being progressively modified to reflect the user feedback.

While the course is designed for end users, with minimal adaptations (e.g. including activities such as discussions on how to approach specific communities/audiences or adapt a use case, or flipped classroom activities) it is suitable for ToT courses.

3 Learning Objectives

By the end of this course, students will be able to:

- 1) Understand of basic OS/FAIR/RDM concepts
- 2) Recognise OS/FAIR principles and practices in the Solid Earth Sciences, and within the EPOS infrastructure in particular
- 3) Use the EPOS Data Portal to discover and reuse FAIR data and scientific products

4 Modules

The course is composed of 2 mandatory modules:

4.1 Module 1 - An introduction to Open Science, FAIR Principles and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences – Open Science, FAIR and EPOS

An overview of basic Open Science and FAIR RDM concepts with examples from the field of SES, and an introduction to how Open and FAIR principles are implemented in practice within the EPOS RI, with some references to its global counterparts.

4.2 Module 2 - Introduction of the EPOS Infrastructure and EPOS Data Portal Walkthrough

Brief presentation of the EPOS infrastructure and demonstration of how the EPOS data portal can be used to discover, visualise, and reuse SES data and scientific products. This module introduces the hands-on session.

4.2.1 Hands-on session

In this session, participants are invited to access the EPOS Data portal, presented with one or more scientific use cases and asked to use the portal to complete some tasks related to the use case. They can self-assess their performance through a form, and provide feedback on the difficulties they find. A facilitator is available the whole time to answer questions and provide tips, and they provide a walkthrough the exercises at the end of the session.

4.3 Optional Modules

Two more optional modules are offered that can be used depending on the prevalent audience:

4.3.1 Module 0 - Data, Databases and Data Sharing in Solid Earth Sciences: An Introduction - From Basic Definitions to the European Regulation

A 101 module especially useful for undergraduates, PHD students, secondary school teachers etc providing general definitions of data, datasets, databases as well as basic orientation regarding RDM in the context of Solid Earth Science

4.3.2 Module 3 - Focus on Interoperability: The EPOS Approach

A more technical discussion of interoperability in the context of SES Research Infrastructures and EPOS in particular, suitable for learners who have more time and interest in getting more information about how the RI works, IT people, Data Providers and Research Infrastructure professionals.

5 Grading Policy

At the moment, we only provide certificates of attendance. However, it is possible to opt for a simple grading policy assigning points for:

- Participation
- Completion of hands-on tests
- (For summer schools only): final project

Grading Scale for exercises and projects would be:

- A = 90-100%
- B = 80-89%
- C = 70-79%
- D = 60-69%
- F = Below 60%

6 Course Policies

Participation to the courses is free of charge. For classroom event travel/accommodation support can be provided in specific occasions. When this happen, information about eligibility and priority criteria will be provided to registrants.

EPOS is firmly dedicated to advancing diversity, equality and inclusion in every training opportunity we offer. We invite registrations from individuals of diverse ethnicities, cultural and religious backgrounds, genders, sexual orientations, and at all stages of their careers.

7 Updates and Versions

As for most domains, the knowledge and practices in the field of Open Science and Research Data Management for Solid Earth Science evolve with time. Always make sure you are using the latest version of the materials. Each file is provided with information about the version and last update. If you have any questions related to the materials, their version, and/or more generally to the EPOS Research Infrastructure or EPOS Data portal please contact us at the address given above.

Appendix II. List of course materials

<i>Title</i>	<i>Type of Resource</i>	<i>Format</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>DOI</i>	<i>Version #</i>	<i>Last Updated dd/mm/yyyy</i>
Facilitator Guide	Document	.docx	A guide to use these materials to organise a training, addressing different aspects of the organisation and delivery of the training (format, layout, description of the activities, etc)	10.5281/zenodo.13684030	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Module 1	Slides	.pptx	A commented slide set for Module 1: An Introduction To Open Science, FAIR Principles And RDM In Solid Earth Sciences – Open Science, FAIR And EPOS	10.5281/zenodo.13682346	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Module 2	Slides	.pptx	A commented slide set for Module 2: Introduction of The EPOS Infrastructure And EPOS Data Portal Walkthrough	10.5281/zenodo.13682395	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Module 0	Slides	.pptx	A commented slideset for optional Module 0: Data, Databases And Data Sharing In Solid Earth Sciences: An Introduction - From Basic Definitions To The European Regulation	10.5281/zenodo.13646663	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Module 3	Slides	.pptx	A commented slide set for optional Module 3: Focus On Interoperability: The EPOS Approach	10.5281/zenodo.13682758	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Collection of Use Cases	Document	.docx	A collection of use cases to be used in the walkthrough and hands-on sessions, and of the	10.5281/zenodo.13683829	V1.0.0	03/09/2024

Learning Path and Training Materials on OS and RDM in Solid Earth Sciences

			related information for hands-on assessment.			
Training questionnaire & feedback form	Spreadsheet	.xlsx	A spreadsheet including: 1) pre-event questions to get to know the audience, 2) tasks, questions, hints and answers for each of the proposed use cases, to be used to guide the hands-on session and assessing the results; 3) post-training questions, to collect feedback on the training and on the user experience with the portal	10.5281/zenodo.13683829	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
List of Additional Links and Resources	Document	.docx	A file proposing a list of additional resources that training facilitators can use for providing additional materials, or students can use to to deepen some of the topics covered during the training	10.5281/zenodo.13646487	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Licence	Text file	.txt	Legal text of the CCby 4.0 international licence, under which these materials are offered.	(provided in this deliverable pack)	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
ReadMe	Text file	.txt	General information on the course, to be provided together with the training materials folder	(provided in this deliverable pack)	V1.0.0	03/09/2024
Citation	Text file	.cff	A machine-readable file that provides proper attribution for the training course	(provided in this deliverable pack)	V1.0.0	03/09/2024